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DETERMINANTS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH: THE CASE OF KAZAKHSTAN

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ABSTRACT

The determinants of economic growth have been the subject of important academic studies for numerous years. Considering the differences in the development levels of countries, there is no consensus on which factors are more effective in growth. For this reason, identifying the factors that determine economic growth remains interesting to determine the growth potential of countries and creating appropriate policies. This study examines the impact of various variables, including gross domestic product (GDP), gross domestic product per capita, trade openness, labor force participation rate, primary school enrollment, gross capital formation, and foreign direct investment, on economic growth in the Kazakhstan economy from 1991 to 2021. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) test method was employed for the research. According to the findings got from the study shows that increases in gross domestic product (GDP) and the gross domestic product per capita (GDPPER) in the short term, and in the long term, increases in openness, labor force participation rate (LABOR), and primary school enrollment levels have a positive impact on economic growth. While the gross capital formation (GCF) variable, whose impact on economic growth was measured in the study, was found to have a negative effect on economic growth in the short term, it was determined that the Foreign direct investment (FDI) variable was not statistically significant on economic growth in both the short and long term.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, Economic Growth, Determinants of Economic Growth, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model.

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IQTISODIY O'SISHNING DETERMINANTLARI: QOZOG'ISTON MISOLIDIDA

ANNOTATSIYA

Iqtisodiy o'sishning determinantlari ko'p yillar davomida muhim ilmiy tadqiqotlar mavzusi bo'lib kelgan. Mamlakatlarning rivojlanish darajasidagi tafovutlar hisobga olinsa, qaysi omillar o'sishda samaraliroq ekani borasida konsensus yo'q. Shu sababli, iqtisodiy o'sishni belgilovchi omillarni aniqlash, mamlakatlarning o'sish salohiyatini aniqlash va tegishli siyosatni yaratish uchun qiziqarli bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqot turli xil o'zgaruvchilar, jumladan yalpi ichki mahsulot (YaIM), aholi jon boshiga yalpi ichki mahsulot, savdo ochiqligi, ishchi kuchi ishtiroki darajasi, boshlang'ich maktabga kirish, yalpi kapital shakllanishi va to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar Qozog'istonda iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'sirini o'rganadi. 1991 yildan 2021 yilgacha iqtisodiyot. Tadqiqot uchun avtoregressiv taqsimlangan kechikish (ARDL) test usuli ishlatilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, yalpi ichki mahsulot (YaIM) va aholi jon boshiga to'g'ri keladigan yalpi ichki mahsulot (YaIM) qisqa muddatda o'sishi, uzoq muddatli istiqbolda esa ochiqlik, ishchi kuchi ishtiroki darajasi (MEHBKAT), boshlang'ich maktabni qamrab olish darajasi esa iqtisodiy o'sishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotda iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'siri o'lchangan yalpi kapital shakllanishi (GCF) o'zgaruvchisi qisqa muddatda iqtisodiy o'sishga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi aniqlangan bo'lsa-da, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar (TDI) o'zgaruvchisi emasligi aniqlandi. qisqa muddatli va uzoq muddatli iqtisodiy o'sish bo'yicha statistik ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: Qozog'iston, Iqtisodiy o'sish, Iqtisodiy o'sishning determinantlari, Avtoregressiv taqsimlangan kechikish (ARDL) modeli.

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ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА: ПРИМЕР КАЗАХСТАНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Детерминанты экономического роста на протяжении многих лет были предметом важных научных исследований. Учитывая различия в уровнях развития стран, не существует единого мнения о том, какие факторы более эффективны для роста. По этой причине выявление факторов, определяющих экономический рост, остается интересным для определения потенциала роста стран и разработки соответствующей политики. В данном исследовании рассматривается влияние различных переменных, включая валовой внутренний продукт (ВВП), валовой внутренний продукт на душу населения, открытость торговли, уровень экономической активности, охват начальным образованием, валовое накопление капитала и прямые иностранные инвестиции, на экономический рост в Казахстане. экономики с 1991 по 2021 год. Для исследования был использован метод авторегрессионного распределенного лага (ARDL). Результаты исследования показывают, что увеличение валового внутреннего продукта (ВВП) и валового внутреннего продукта на душу населения (ВВПЕР) в краткосрочной и долгосрочной перспективе, увеличение открытости, уровня участия рабочей силы (ТРУД), а уровень охвата начальным образованием оказывает положительное влияние на экономический рост. Хотя было обнаружено, что переменная валового накопления капитала (ВКФ), влияние которой на экономический рост измерялось в исследовании, оказывает негативное влияние на экономический рост в краткосрочной перспективе, было установлено, что переменная прямых иностранных инвестиций (ПИИ) не была статистически значимы для экономического роста как в краткосрочной, так и в долгосрочной перспективе.

Ключевые слова: Казахстан, экономический рост, детерминанты экономического роста, модель авторегрессии с распределенным лагом (ARDL).

INTRODUCTION

The concept of economic growth is one of the most prominent indicators used to measure development and high social welfare in countries. The concept of growth, which became more important after the Second World War, has become more important with the increase in globalization and financialisation movements (Byankarelli and Krepski, 2014). Activities to increase real growth in economies where financialisation is intense are important to create policies to determine the stability of countries, especially employment, foreign trade balance, inflation, and exchange rates. Economic growth has been tried to be explained by various theoretical models of different economic schools. Defining the determinants of economic growth within internal and external growth models and creating policies to increase economic growth have been defined as the main elements in determining the welfare and development levels of countries (Weil, 2016). The classic Solow (1956) model defined the main determinants of growth in terms of population growth, savings level, investments, capital accumulation, and technological development level. In the Solow (1956) model, positive changes in the variables in question will increase the level of convergence of underdeveloped countries to the level of developed countries (Brock and Taylor, 2010). The Solow-Swan (1956) model explains the country's long-term growth power with the increase in productive capacity resulting from capital accumulation, population growth, labor force, and technological development (Guerrini, 2006). Unlike the Solow (1956) and Solow-Swan (1956) models, the Rebello-AK model uses a linear production function in which growth is related to the development of the capital stock. According to the model, which shows that economic growth depends on the increase in investment, achieving sustainable economic growth becomes possible by implementing policies that increase investments (McGrattan, 1998). Besides classical growth models, Acemoglu and Robinson (2001, 2006, 2012) argue that the development levels of countries are related to their existing institutional infrastructures. According to this approach, the way countries are classified in the global economy is closely related to their institutional development levels. In countries with higher levels of institutional development, economic growth, and social welfare develop to the same extent (Acemoğlu and Robinson, 2008). The growth policies implemented by countries are it is built on important economic policies such as development, level of development and increase in social welfare. In this context, the concept of growth, which has a wide range of meaning and scope, and the determinants of economic growth, are discussed from a wide perspective in the literature (Cinel, 2014).

Growth is a concept far beyond economics. It has great strategic importance for the future of countries and societies. Growth is important for developing countries as well as developed countries. Growth is so important for the future of societies and countries brings with it some macroeconomic problems (United Nations, 2013). The inability of countries to achieve the desired levels of economic growth targets or to achieve sustainability in economic growth are the main macroeconomic problems that numerous countries frequently encounter today. The main reasons for these macroeconomic problems seen in country e' economies are directly related to the differences in the economic growth dynamics of the countries (Kurzenev and Matveenko, 2017). Therefore, the richness, differences, diversity, development levels and other important factors in the growth dynamics of countries cause differences in growth rates between countries. As the determining actors of the long-term economic growth seen in the country's economies such as political stability, economic stability, capital accumulation, foreign investments, technological development, human capital, rich natural resources, income distribution, employment, population growth rate, unemployment rate, inflation (Lavrov, 2006). Depending on these factors, there are differences in the growth dynamics between country's economies. While it was seen that the free economy model was implemented in numerous countries' economies until the 1990s, in Kazakhstan; It is seen that the economic model affiliated with the Soviet Socialist Republic Union (SSCI) is implemented (Aristenbekov, 2006). The economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which declared its independence with the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991, was turbulent until the 2000s. Especially after the collapse of the Soviet Union, the sharp decline in the demand for heavy industry and metals in Kazakhstan negatively affected the country's economy. Policy makers, who focused on structural reforms and privatizations in the economy until the 2000s, later switched to the free market economic model and adopted the open growth model (Kuzmina,

2013). Kazakhstan, which prioritizes the dominant actors who are effective actors of economic growth, has successfully carried this power to the present day and has become one of the most developed countries in Central Asia today (Georgieva, 2023).

In this study, the determinants of economic growth in the Kazakhstan economy in the period covering the years 1991-2021 were investigated. After the introduction part, a literature review on the determinants of economic growth associated with various factors is presented in the second chapter. Following the literature review, the data set considered as the determinants of economic growth is presented in the third section and the methodology to be applied in the study is included. While the fourth part of the study comprises empirical findings, the fifth part includes the results of the study.

RELATED LITERATURE

There are many theoretical and empirical studies on the determinants of economic growth. In these studies, economic growth is directly related to external factors, internal factors, and the growth dynamics of countries. Therefore, it is seen that the economies of the countries, which have the dominant forces that determine economic growth, achieve their growth targets in a shorter time with the correct policies they implement. It is seen that the economies of countries that are weak and unsuccessfully managed in this context can either reach their growth targets after long periods or never reach them. In this study, which is specifically addressed in Kazakhstan, it is seen that most of the dominant factors that determine economic growth in the country exist. However, the country's economy, which remained dependent on the Soviets for a long time, could not recover for a long time because of the crises that emerged with the dissolution of the Soviets. The country's economy, which went through a recovery period between 1991 and 2001, achieved political and economic stability as of 2001 with its rich natural resources and direct foreign investments coming to the country. The establishment of general stability in Kazakhstan is intrinsically linked to the country's economic growth, which surpasses that of other Central Asian nations. In this context, when studies on the determinants of economic growth are examined, for example, Barro (1996) conducted a panel data set analysis with data got from approximately 100 countries on the determinants of economic growth in the period between 1960 and 1990. According to the results of the analysis, it is emphasized that political freedom has a weak effect on growth and also has a non-linear relationship. He also stated that limited political freedom would positively affect economic growth. Ciccone and Jaracinski (2010) studied the determinants of economic growth by considering the income forecasts of different countries in the period between 1960 and 1996. In this study, the PWT 6.2 benchmark model was applied. According to the study results, there are numerous factors that hinder or encourage economic growth. These can be listed as the international trade of countries, the demographic structure of the country and the positive or negative effects of the geography where the countries are on growth. Chirwa and Odhiambo (2016) discussed an empirical study on developed and developing countries in their study on macroeconomic determinants of economic growth. According to this study, the main macroeconomic determinants of economic growth in developing countries are; They found it directly related to issues such as foreign direct investments, foreign aid, fiscal policies, demographic structure, natural resources, and monetary policy. In developed countries, the determinants of economic growth is related to issues such as human capital, physical capital, monetary policy, population, and technological development. Bruns and Ioannidis (2020) discussed 37 growth determinants using the Bayesian Model Average method in their study, covering the period between 1960 and 2010. According to the findings of the study suggested that there is an instability between growth periods and the determinants of growth. In addition, findings show that some growth determinants, such as education and demographics, are more influential than others. Wha and Hong (2012) applied the Conditional convergence model in their study on the determinants of economic growth in Asia. According to the study, Asia has drawn a strong growth model based on capital accumulation in the last 30 years. They also stated that increasing the level of education, protection of property rights and investments in R&D also affected growth positively. Chen (2002), in his survey study on the determinants of economic growth in East Asia, focused on the determinants of growth from the 1950s to the present. According to the results, the harmonious relationship between technological development and total factor productivity comes to the fore as the dominant factor of growth in East

Asia economies. Agayev and Yamak (2010). In the period between 1995 and 2006, they tried to reveal the determinants of economic growth in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States and the parts of economic growth with data set and panel data set models. In the study, they argued that macroeconomic stability and permanent flexible transformation reforms support sustainable growth in transition economies such as the CIS. They also stated that the effect of democratization on growth is uncertain. Oralbaykızı (2019) discussed the relationship between human capital and economic growth in the Central Asian Turkish republics in the period between 1991 and 2016. Panel data analysis method was used in the study. Results of the analysis stated that there is a harmonious relationship between human capital and economic growth variables in Central Asian countries in the long term. Agraval (2008) studied the relationship between poverty reduction and economic growth in Kazakhstan. In this empirical study, he showed the steps taken and investments made to reduce poverty in Kazakhstan as the most important factor affecting economic growth in the country. Amin and Ainekova (2012) examined the factors affecting the growth of the Kazakhstan economy in the long term. In this empirical study, they found a positive result between country dynamics and Total Factor Productivity. According to this result, it is showed that economic growth will be achieved by using the growth dynamics of the country efficiently. Katenova and Nurmakhonova (2017) tried to explain the growth relationship between financial development and the Kazakhstan economy. In this study, they concluded that the financial development factor positively affects growth in the country's economy. Zhanarys and Bakyt (2021) discussed the relationship between transportation and logistics and economic growth in the Kazakhstan economy in the period between 1995 and 2019. Total production, demand, and vector error correction models were used in this study. According to the Granger test results, a bidirectional causality and effect relationship was determined between the railway transportation infrastructure and economic growth. The findings showed that the road and maritime transport conditions in Kazakhstan should be improved in order to promote economic growth. It has also been stated that economic growth will gain momentum and be sustainable with the development of a long-term transportation policy. Mirzabekkızi, Keneşbaev, Razakova et al. (2022) studied the relationship between economic growth, energy production and technological investments in Kazakhstan between 1993 and 2020. Cointegration and Vector Error correction models were used in this study. The result of the study it was concluded that energy production in the country plays an important role in the growth of the Kazakhstan economy. Furthermore, it has been indicated that the effect of technology investments on growth exceeds the growth rate achieved through energy production.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In this study, the determinants of economic growth in the Kazakhstan economy between 1991-2021 were investigated. In the literature, the determinants of economic growth are defined through different variables. For example, Iqbal and Zahid (1998) used the variables real Gross Domestic Product (real GDP), per capita real income, middle and high school enrolment as a ratio to total employed labor force, trade openness, external debt, overall budgeted deficit as determinants of economic growth. Anaman (2004) used the variables real GDP, population, gross capital formation, export, import, and labor force in his study, examining the long-term determinants of economic growth. Ajide (2014) used economic freedom, foreign direct investment (FDI), labor, life expectancy, openness variables to investigate the determinants of economic growth in the Nigerian economy. Boldenau and Constantinescu (2015) define the main variables that have the most impact on economic growth as natural resources, capital goods, human sources, and technology. Jerez and Chasco (2016) used school enrollment variables as a measure of institutional quality index, FDI, trade openness, life expectancy, and human capital as determinants of economic growth. Bruns and Ioannidis (2020) modeled demography, education, trade, and investment variables as determinants of economic growth. Ali (2022) examined the determinants of economic growth with foreign debt, financial stability, and exchange rate volatility variables. Besides these studies, the variables carbon emissions, clean energy investments, financial development, energy efficiency, green innovation have recently been used in the literature to define the economic growth (Zahoor et al., 2022; Khan et al. 2022; Ning et al. 2023; Razzaq et al. 2023). In this study, the variables included in the studies of

Iqbal and Zahid (1998) and Anaman (2004) were taken as the basis of determinants of economic growth in Kazakhstan. The reason for following these authors is that the sample size and variable structure of the data sets to be used to create the determinants of economic growth in the Kazakhstan economy are limited. For this reason, in the study, a data set was created based on the maximum sample that could be reached as determinants of economic growth. In this direction, the study examines real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), per capita real income (GDPPER), foreign direct investment (FDI), gross capital formation (GCF), labor force participation (LABOR), primary school enrollment as a ratio as determinants of economic growth. Total employed labor force (SCHOOL) and trade openness are defined as the ratio of exports plus imports over GDP (TO). All variables used in the study were taken from the World Bank database as % change.

In the study, first, the stationarity of the series subject to analysis was examined with Augmented-Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests. After determining stationarity of the series and making the non-stationary series stationary by taking their differences, the long- and short-term relationship between the series was examined with the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. In the ARDL bounds test, the cointegration relationship can be examined when the independent variables are I(0) or I(1), provided that the dependent variable is I(1). The long and short-term coefficients of the ARDL model developed by Pesaran et al. (2001) were estimated through the following equations:

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_1 \Delta GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_2 \Delta GDPPER_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_3 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_4 \Delta GCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_5 \Delta LABOR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_6 \Delta SCHOOL_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_7 \Delta TO_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_1 \Delta GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_2 \Delta GDPPER_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_3 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_4 \Delta GCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_5 \Delta LABOR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_6 \Delta SCHOOL_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_7 \Delta TO_{t-i} + \beta_8 ECM_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \quad (2)$$

ARDL model long and short-term equations are shown in equations (1) and (2). In equation (2), the error correction term (ECT) defines the short-term relationship between the variables. The existence of a short-term relationship between the series depends on the condition that the ECT term is negative and statistically significant.

In order to apply the ARDL test method, the lag length must first be determined. The lag length was determined through the Vector Autoregressive model. Pesaran et al. (2001) and Narayan (2004) state that if annual data is used in ARDL model estimation, the optimal lag length should be taken as 2 at most. In this direction, a VAR (2) model was created and the appropriate lag length was determined according to LR, FPE, SC, AIC, and HQ information criteria. After determining the lag length, the ARDL model was created and the boundary test was first applied. The calculated F statistics value was compared with the lower and upper bond values defined for 1%, 5% and 10%. That the F statistic value is greater than the upper bond value shows that there is a cointegration relationship between the series. After investigating the cointegration relationship between the series, the long- and short-term relationship was investigated and the consistency and reliability of the findings were examined through Cusum and Cusum of Squares (CUSUMQ) graphs.

EMPRICAL RESULTS

In the study, first, the stationarity of the series was examined with ADF and PP unit root tests. According to the constant ADF unit root results seen in Table 1, it was found that the GDP, GCF, LABOR, and SCHOOL series were not stationary at their level values, while the GDPPER, FDI and TO series were stationary at the 10%, 5% and 1% significance levels, respectively. According to the constant and trend ADF unit root test results, FDI and TO are stationary at 10% and 5% significance levels. PP unit root test results show that FDI and SCHOOL series are stationary at 10% significance level and TO series are stationary at 1% significance level. According to the constant and trend PP test results, only the TO series is stationary at the 1% significance level. In Table 1, the results show that the non-stationary series are stationary when their first differences are taken.

Table 1: ADF and PP Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Constant		Constant and Trend	
	ADF	PP	ADF	PP
s				

	Level	First Diff	Level	First Diff	Level	First Diff	Level	First Diff
GDP	-2.444	-5.051***	-2.617	-6.174***	-2.144	5.051** *	-1.946	-7.358***
GDPPER	-2.632*	-5.599***	-2.651	-6.284***	-2.349	5.599** *	-2.640	-7.399***
FDI	-3.373**	-8.119***	-3.293*	-9.229***	-3.354*	8.119** *	-3.232	21.416** *
GCF	-2.009	-6.635***	-2.502	-6.923***	-2.353	6.630** *	-2.294	-7.576***
LABOR	-2.257	-3.942***	-2.257	-3.852***	-2.500	3.850** *	-2.500	-3.539***
SCHOOL	-2.852	12.896** *	-2.899*	-4.640***	-2.541	4.806** *	-2.529	-4.806***
TO	4.083** *	-8.199*	4.042** *	12.265** *	4.062* *	8.235** *	4.062** *	24.673** *

Note: McKinnon critical values to rejected the null hypothesis is -3.670, -2.963 and -2.621, respectively.

The optimal lag length was investigated with the help of the VAR(p) model in order to find stationarity of the series, to make the non-stationary series stationary by taking their differences, and then to find the cointegration relationship between the series. According to the model results estimated as VAR(2), the optimal delay length was found to be 1 according to the LR, FPE, SC, and HQ criteria. However, when diagnostic tests regarding the VAR(1) model results were applied, it was found that there was an autocorrelation problem in the VAR(1) model and the characteristic roots of the VAR(1) model were not consistent. Therefore, the VAR(2) model was estimated by taking the optimal lag length as 2. Diagnostic tests of the VAR(2) model have revealed that this model is reliable and consistent. Diagnostic tests for the VAR(2) model are presented in the Appendix.

Table 2. ARDL Model Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	496.1754	NA	9589473.	35.94110	36.27415	36.04292
1	391.8931	148.9748*	207259.9*	31.99236	34.65677*	32.80690*
2	342.6285	45.74563	434557.2	31.97347*	36.96923	33.50072

Note: * indicates lag order selected by the criterion, LR:sequential modified LR test statistic, FPE: Final predictor error, AIC: Akaike information criterion, SC: Schwarz information criterion, HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

After finding the optimal lag length, the ARDL Bound Test was used to examine whether there was a cointegration relationship between the series. The results got from the model established as ARDL (2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1) are shown in Table 3. According to Table 3, the F statistics value was found to be 6.413. Since the sample set of the analysis comprised 28 observations, the test results were compared with the lower and upper critical values of 30 observations. It was seen that the calculated F statistics value was greater than the upper bound value at the 1% significance level and it was concluded that there was a cointegration relationship between the series.

Table 3. ARDL Bound Test Results

Model	k	N	F Statistics	Signif.	Lower	Upper
					Bound I(0)	Bound I(1)
ARDL(2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1)	6	28	6.413***	10%	2.334	3.515
				5%	2.794	4.148
				1%	3.976	5.691

Note: k defines the number of independent variables, N defines the time dimension of the sample, *** defines the 1% significance level.

Table 4 shows the long-term analysis results of the ARDL (2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1) model. According to the findings, a one-unit increase in the previous value of GDP reduces economic growth by 13%, and a one-unit decrease in the previous period's value of GCF reduces economic growth by 0.3%. A one unit increase in the previous value of GDPPER increases economic growth by 16%. A one unit increase in TO increases economic growth by 0.01%. When we look at the LABOR and SCHOOL series, it is concluded that both series have a significant and long-term positive effect on economic growth at the 10% and 5% significance levels, respectively. On the other hand, it was found that the effect of the FDI variable on economic growth in the long term was not statistically significant.

Table 4. ARDL Long-Term Test Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t- Statistic	Prob.
C	0.1292	0.1341	0.9631	0.354
GDP(-1)	0.1374	0.0431	-3.1840	0.007***
GDPPER(-1)	0.1675	0.0502	3.3316	0.006***
FDI(-1)	-0.0158	0.0225	-0.7008	0.496
GCF (-1)	-0.0316	0.0096	-3.2931	0.006***
LABOR(-1)	-0.0734	0.2958	-0.2482	0.808
SCHOOL(-1)	0.0329	0.0325	1.0102	0.332
TO(-1)	0.0123	0.0067	1.8396	0.090*
D(GDP(-1))	-0.0305	0.0206	-1.4787	0.165
D(GDPPER)	1.0478	0.0246	42.564	0.000***
D(FDI)	0.0062	0.0151	0.4122	0.6874
D(GCF)	-0.0159	0.0058	-2.7182	0.018**
D(LABOR)	0.3287	0.1619	-2.0304	0.0651*
D(SCHOOL)	0.0469	0.0199	2.3568	0.0363**
D(SCHOOL1(-1))	0.0268	0.0153	1.7529	0.105
D(TO)	0.0067	0.0038	1.7574	0.104

Note: *, ** and *** define significance levels of 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Short-term test results of the ARDL (2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1) model can be seen in Table 5. Short-term test results reveal that variables other than FDI have a statistically significant impact on economic growth in the short term. According to Table 5, a one-unit increase in the previous value of the GDP variable will increase the economic growth by 0.03%, a one-unit increase in the GDPPER variable will increase the economic growth by 1.04%. A one-unit increase in LABOR will increase the economic growth by 32%. One-unit increase in the value of SCHOOL increases economic growth by 0.04%, and a one-unit increase in the lagged value of SCHOOL increases economic growth by 0.02%. A one unit change in GCF reduces economic growth by 0.01%. The error correction coefficient (CointEq) of the model was found to be negative and statistically significant. According to this result, a one-unit deviation ($1/-0.1374=7.28$) that will occur in the short term will be corrected by 7.28% every year in the long term and will converge to balance again. When the diagnostic test results of the model are examined, they show that there is no autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, or model building error in the model and that the model is reliable and consistent.

Table 5. ARDL Short-Term Test Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GDP(-1))	0.0305	0.0119	-2.5635	0.024**
D(GDPPER)	1.0478	0.0113	92.048	0.000***
D(FDI)	0.0062	0.0081	0.7706	0.455
D(GCF)	-0.0159	0.0031	-4.9908	0.000***
D(LABOR)	0.3287	0.0909	-3.6135	0.003***
D(SCHOOL)	0.0469	0.0118	3.9544	0.001***
D(SCHOOL(-1))	0.0268	0.0094	2.8422	0.014**
D(TO)	0.0067	0.0017	3.7720	0.002***
CointEq(-1)*	-0.1374	0.0152	-9.0134	0.000***
R-squared	0.798755	BPG	0.7679	
Adjusted R-squared	0.728230	BG	0.1144	
S.E. of regression	0.165094	JB	1.3224	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.402547	RAMSEY	0.1687	

Note: *, ** and *** define significance levels of 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Figure 1 tests whether there is a structural break in the model with short and long-term relationships. When the Cusum and CusumQ graphs are examined, it is seen that the graphs tested at the 5% significance level of both graphs are within critical limits. This result shows that the long-term relationships between the variables are consistent and there is no structural break in the series.

Figure 1. Cusum and Cusum of Squares Graphs

CONCLUSION

Extensive research in the literature has been focused on understanding the various factors that drive economic growth. The question of which factors impact economic growth and which factors should be prioritized in reducing growth disparities between countries remains an area of ongoing debate in the literature. Besides studies focusing on traditional macroeconomic variables as drivers of economic growth, there has been a significant increase in studies examining the connection between economic growth and environmental factors in recent times. Considering the relationship between economic growth and social welfare, it becomes more important for countries to develop policies to increase real growth and stability. The fact that the factors affecting economic growth in the literature often focus on European economies is far from providing solutions for the policies that Central Asian economies should follow independence. In this context, this study aimed to examine the determinants of economic growth in the Kazakhstan economy during the period of 1991-2021 by employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) test method. The main findings of the study show that the gross domestic product (GDP) and the gross domestic product per capita (GDPPER)

are the primary factors influencing economic growth in the short term within the Kazakhstan economy. In other words, the analysis found that past real GDP and per capita real GDP values strongly influenced the present growth rate. Variables such as the rate of openness, labor force participation rate (LABOR), and primary school enrollment (SCHOOL) have a positive impact on long-term economic growth. In short-term results, it is apparent that the previous values of the GDP, GDPPER, LABOR, and SCHOOL variables have a statistically significant and positive effect on the present period of economic growth, in a manner consistent with the long-term findings. In the short term, it was observed that gross capital formation (GCF) had a statistically significant and adverse impact on economic growth. Foreign direct investment (FDI) variable was found to be statistically insignificant in the short and long term.

APPENDIX

VAR(2) model Fit Results for ARDL Lag Order Selection Criteria

Roots of Characteristic Polynomial	
Root	Modulus
0.876960 - 0.202767i	0.900097
0.876960 + 0.202767i	0.900097
-0.346154 - 0.751511i	0.827400
-0.346154 + 0.751511i	0.827400
0.252303 - 0.744509i	0.786098
0.252303 + 0.744509i	0.786098
-0.622360 - 0.353401i	0.715698
-0.622360 + 0.353401i	0.715698
0.612611	0.612611
0.079353 - 0.525840i	0.531794
0.079353 + 0.525840i	0.531794
-0.381142	0.381142
0.002223 - 0.251157i	0.251167
0.002223 + 0.251157i	0.251167

Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

Иқтибослар/Сноски/References

1. Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, J. (2008). *The role of institutions in growth and development* (Vol. 10). Washington, DC: World Bank.
2. Agraval, P. (2008). Economic Growth and Poverty Reduction: Evidence from Kazakhstan, *Asian Development Review*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 90–115.
3. Aғayev, S. Ve Yamak, N. (2010). Bağımsız Devletler Topluluğu Ülkelerinde Ekonomik Büyümenin Belirleyicileri, *Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, Cilt: 23, Sayı: 4.
4. Ajide, K. B. (2014). Determinants of Economic Growth in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics (JAS)*, 5(2).
5. Ali, A. (2022). Foreign Debt, Financial Stability, Exchange Rate Volatility and Economic Growth in South Asian Countries. MPRA Paper 116099, University Library of Munich, Germany.
6. Amin, A.A. ve Ainekova, D. (2012). The Long Run Growth Rate of the Kazakhstan's Economy, *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics* 2012, 5 (9), 45-56.
7. Anaman, K. A. (2004). Determinants of economic growth in Brunei Darussalam. *Journal of Asian Economics*, Elsevier, 15(4), pp. 777-796.
8. Arıstenbekov K. (2006). Экономический рост Казахстан в контексте мировой экономики. *Вопросы экономики*, (11), 133-146.
9. Barro, R.J. (1996). Determinants of Economic Growth: A Cross-Country Empirical Study, NBER, National Bureau of Economic Research, Working Paper 5698, *Annals Of Economics And Finance* 4, 231–274 (2003).
10. Birlermiş Milletler, (2013). Руководство по формированию национальной политики в сфере занятости, Международная организация труда.
11. Boldenau, F.T. & Constantinescu, L. (2015). The Main Determinant Affecting Economic Growth. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Braşov Series V: Economic Sciences*, Vol. 8 (57), No. 2
12. Brock, W. A., & Taylor, M. S. (2010). The green Solow model. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 15, 127-153.
13. Buruns, S.B. & Ioannidis, J.P.A. (2020). Determinants of Economic Growth: Different Time Different Answer? *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 63().
14. Буанкаравелли, А.М. ve Крепски, К.У. (2014). Экономический рост и социальное развитие: опыт Бразилии, Неравенство доходов и экономический рост: стратегии выхода из кризиса, *Журнал «Альтернативы»*.
15. Chen, E.K.Y. (2002). The Total Factor Productivity Debate: Determinants of Economic Growth in East Asia, *Asian-Pacific Economic Literature Volume 11, Issue 1* p. 18-38.
16. Chirwa, T.G. ve Odhiambo, N.M. (2016). Macroeconomic Determinants Of Economic Growth: A Review Of International Literature, *South East European Journal of Economics and Business* Volume 11 (2) 2016, 33-47.
17. Ciccone, A. ve Marek J. (2010). "Determinants of Economic Growth: Will Data Tell?" *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 2 (4): 222-46.
18. Cinel, E.A. (2014). Türkiye'de Ekonomik Büyümenin Belirleyicileri (1980-2011), *Ordu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü* 01-04-2014.
19. Georgieva, K. (2023). «Золотой потенциал» экономических реформ в странах Кавказа и Центральной Азии, *Mejduranodniy Balyutniy Fond*.
20. Guerrini, L. (2006). The Solow–Swan model with a bounded population growth rate. *Journal of Mathematical Economics*, 42(1), 14-21.
21. Iqbal, Z. & Zahid, G.M. (1998). Macroeconomic Determinants of Economic Growth in Pakistan. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 37(2), pp. 125-148.
22. Jerez, V., Daniel H. & Yrigoyen Coro (2016). Long-Run Determinants of Economic Growth in South America. *Journal of Applied Economics*, 19(1), pp. 169-192.

23. Katenova, M. ve Nurmakhonova, M. (2012). Financial Development and Economic Growth : The Case of Kazakhstan, *International Review of Business Research Papers* Vol. 13. No. 1. March 2017 Issue. Pp. 151 – 160.
24. Khan,I., Zakari,A.,Dagar,V. & Singh,S. (2022). World Energy Trilemma and Transformative Energy Developments as Determinants of Economic Growth Amid Environmental Sustainability. *Energy Economics*,Volume 108().
25. Kurzenev, B. A. ve Матвеевко, В. Д. (2017). *Экономический рост*. " Издательский дом"" Питер""".
26. Kuzmina, E. M. (2013). Социально-экономическая динамика постсоветского Казахстана. *Российский экономический журнал*, (5), 77-89.
27. Lavrov, EI, K. E. A. (2006). *Экономический рост: теории и проблемы*.
28. Lee, J.W. ve Hong, K. (2012). Economic growth in Asia: Determinants and prospects, *Japan and the World Economy*, Volume 24, Issue 2, Pages 101-113.
29. McGrattan, E. R. (1998). A defense of AK growth
30. models. *Federal Reserve Bank of Minneapolis Quarterly Review*, 22(4), 13-27.
31. Mırzabekkızı, K., Keneşbayev, B. vd. (2022). Analysis of Causality Relationship Between the Economic Growth and the Energy Production and Technological Investments in Kazakhstan, *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 2022, 12(6), 123-126.
32. Narayan,P.K.(2004). Fiji's Tourism Demand: the ARDL Approach to Cointegration. *Tourism Economics*,10(2).
33. Ning, Y., Cherian, J., Sial, M.S.,Oteo,S.A. & Din,M.Z.U.(2023). Green Bond as a New Determinant of Sustainable Green Financing, Energy Efficiency Investment, and Economic Growth: A Global Perspective. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 30, 61324–61339.
34. Oralbaykızı, A.S. (2019). Orta Asya Türk Cumhuriyetlerinde Beşeri Sermaye ve Ekonomik Büyüme İlişkisi, *Kırıkkale University, Journal of Social Sciences*, Volume: 9 Issue: 2, 341 - 360, 01.07.2019.
35. Pesaran, M. H., Y. Shin & R. Smith, 2001, Bounds Testing Approaches to the Analysis of Level Relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(), pp. 289-326.
36. Razzaq, A., Tehreem, F. & Murshed, M. (2023). Asymmetric Effects of Tourism Development and Green Innovation on Economic Growth and Carbon Emissions in Top 10 GDP Countries. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*. 66(),pp. 471-500.
37. Weil, D. (2016). *Economic growth*. Routledge.
38. Zahoor,Z.,Khan,I. & Hou, F. (2022). Clean Energy Investment and Financial Development as Determinants of Environment and Sustainable Economic Growth: Evidence from China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int.* ,29(11),pp.16006-16016.
39. Zhanarys, R. Ve Bakyt, S. (2021). Assessing the impact of transport and logistics on economic growth in emerging economies: a case study for the conditions of the Republic of Kazakhstan, *Transport Problems* 2021 Volume 16 Issue 2.

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